

NUTQNI AVTOMATIK TANIB OLIISHDA QUARTZNET MODELI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada nutqni tanib olishda NVIDIA kompaniyasi tomonidan taklif etilgan neyron tarmog‘i modelini o‘zbek tilidani nutq ma‘lumotlar to‘plami bilan o‘qitish orqali o‘tkazilgan tadqiqotlar bayon etilgan. Hozirgi kunda neyron tarmoqlarning turli modellardan nutqni avtomatik tanib olish tizimlarini yaratishda keng foydalanilmoqda. Bu esa nutqni tanib olish sifatini keskin oshishiga sabab bo‘lmoqda. Nutqni tanib olishning mavjud tizimlari turli neyron tarmoq modellari asosida ishlashga mo‘ljallangan. Mazkur maqola ana shunday modellardan birini nutqni avtomatik tanib olishda qo‘llanilishiga bag‘ishlangan bo‘lib, unda quartznet modeli va undan foydalanish bo‘yicha ma‘lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: nutqni avtomatik tanib olish, neyron tarmoq modeli, QuartzNet, spektogramma, xatolik funksiyasi, optimizator

1. Kirish

So‘nggi yillarda ko‘plab kompaniyalar nutqni avtomatik tanib olishga mo‘ljallangan tizimlarini taklif etishmoqda. Jumladan, AQSHning NVIDIA kompaniyasi tadqiqotchilari nutqni avtomatik tanib olish tizimida yo‘naltirilgan to‘liq neyron tarmoqdan tashkil topgan akustik modeldan foydalanishni taklif etishdi [1]. Taklif etilgan model bir nechta qoldiqli bloklar [2] va ular orasidagi bog‘lanishlardan tashkil topgan. Modelning har bir bloki bir yoki bir nechta bir o‘lchamli (1D) o‘ramli qatlamlardan, paketli normallashtirish [3] va ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) [4] qatlamlardan tashkil topgan bo‘lib, modelni o‘qitish CTC (Connectionist Temporal Classification) xatolik funksiyasi orqali amalga oshiriladi [5]. Ushbu modelda Jasper (Just Another Speech Recognizer) arxitekturasidagi kodlovchi va dekodlovchi modullaridan foydalanilgan [6]. Ushbu neyron tarmoq modeli LibriSpeech va Wall Street Journal nutq korpuslarida yuqori aniqlik ko‘rsatgan va modelni optimallashtirish natijasida uning parametrlari va giperparametrlari ingliz tilidagi nutqni avtomatik tanib olish uchun sozlangan. Tadqiqotchilar model

giperparametrlari qiymatlariga bog‘liq holda QUARTZNETning bir nechta variantlarini taklif etishgan. Bunda neyron tarmoq modeli parametrlari soni 6,7 - 18,9 million oralig‘ida o‘zgarishi mumkin. Bu nutqni avtomatik tanib olish uchun yo‘naltirilgan mashhur neyron tarmoqli modellardan sezilarli darajada kichik bo‘lib, u modelning nisbatan ixchamligini ta‘minlaydi. Masalan, wav2letter++ [7] da 208 million, LAS (Listen, Attend and Spell) [8] 360 million, Deep Speech 2 modelida esa parametrlar soni 38 million tani tashkil etadi [9]. Model parametrlarini kamligiga qaramay, boshqa modellardan tanib olish aniqligi bo‘yicha qolishmaydi. Modelning ixchamligi uni o‘qitish uchun sarflanadigan vaqt va hisoblash resurslarini tejashga imkon beradi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu modelni boshqa ma‘lumotlar to‘plamiga ham samarali sozlash mumkinligi tadqiqotchilar tomonidan ta‘kidlab o‘tilgan.

2. Asosiy qism

Olib borilgan tajribalarda QuartzNet 15x5 WER (Word error rate) ko‘rsatkichi bo‘yicha til modelidan foydalanmagan holda xalaqitsiz nutq ma‘lumotlari LibriSpeech dev-cleanda o‘rtacha

tanib olish dasturiy vositalarini yaratishda foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

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